

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of 2-phenylimino-3-aryl-4-*S*-benzyl-6-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosylimino-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochlorides

P. T. Agrawal and S. P. Deshmukh*

P.G. Department of Chemistry, Shri Shivaji College, Akola-444 001, Maharashtra, India

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Abstract : Several *N*-lactosylated-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochlorides have been prepared by the interaction of 1-aryl-5-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets and phenyl isocyanodichloride. The structure of these new *N*-lactosylated-1,3,5-thiadiazines have been established on the basis of usual chemical transformations and IR, NMR and Mass spectral analysis. Antimicrobial activities of these compounds were evaluated.

Keywords : 2,4-Isodithiobiurets, phenyl isocyanodichloride, 1,3,5-thiadiazines.

Introduction

Very few compounds containing thioamido group and having lactosyl substituent on nitrogen are known which have been studied for their biological activities. Such *N*-lactosylated derivatives exhibit a wide range of medicinal activities, such as antiviral, antidiabetic, analgesic, anti-tumor and some other activities^{1,2}. A simple method for the synthesis of 1,3,5-thiadiazines has been reported. This was essentially based on the reaction of phenyl isocyanodichloride with thioamido group containing compounds^{3,4}.

In the present communication we report the synthesis of several *N*-lactosylated-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochlorides prepared by the reaction of 1-aryl-5-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets and phenyl isocyanodichloride. The required 1-aryl-5-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets were obtained by the reaction of 1-aryl-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamides with hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl isothiocyanate.

Results and discussion

2-Phenylimino-3-aryl-4-*S*-benzyl-6-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosylimino-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochlorides (**3a-g**) (Scheme 1) were prepared by the condensation of 1-aryl-5-hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**1a-g**) and phenyl isocyanodichloride (**2**) in CHCl₃. After condensation, the solvent was distilled off to obtain a sticky residue. This residue was triturated several times with petroleum ether (60–80 °C,

60 ml) to afford a pale yellow solid (**3a-g**). The product was found to be non-desulphurised when boiled with alkaline lead acetate. IR spectrum of the product shows characteristic absorption of lactose unit in the range of 900–910, 1000–1100 and 1200–1300 cm⁻¹^{5,6}. Mass spectrum showed the characteristics of lactose unit⁷. All the compounds have been screened for both antibacterial and antifungal activity.

Experimental

Specific rotations were measured on Equip-Tronics Digital Polarimeter at 28 °C in CHCl₃. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrum RXI FTIR spectrophotometer (4000–450 cm⁻¹). ¹H NMR was recorded in CDCl₃ on Bruker DRX-300 spectrometer operating at 300 MHz. The Mass spectra were recorded on Jeol-SX-102 (FAB) instrument.

*Preparation of 1-aryl-S-benzyl isothiocarbamides*⁸ :

The required 1-aryl-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamides were prepared by known procedure.

Synthesis of 1-aryl-5-hepta-O-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl-2-S-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (1a-g) :

A benzene solution of 1-phenyl-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamides (0.005 *M*, 1.11 g in 10 ml) was added to benzene solution of hepta-*O*-benzoyl- β -D-lactosyl isothiocyanate (0.005 *M*, 5.5 g in 40 ml of benzene). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was brought to room temperature and evaporated to syrup. This was

where, R = (a) phenyl, (b) *p*-tolyl, (c) *o*-tolyl, (d) *m*-tolyl, (e) *p*-Cl-phenyl, (f) *o*-Cl-phenyl, (g) *m*-Cl-phenyl

Scheme 1

trituated with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) to afford a solid. This was crystallized with acetone-ether, m.p. 140 °C.

Preparation of phenyl isocyanodichloride⁹ (2) :

Phenyl isocyanodichloride was prepared by the interaction of phenyl isothiocyanate and excess of chlorine. Details of a typical experiment are as follows.

Through a chloroformic solution of phenyl isothiocyanate (5 ml in 15 ml chloroform), chlorine (generated from 8 g KMnO_4 and 50 ml conc. HCl) was passed

by maintaining the temperature below 10 °C. After complete addition of chlorine, the yellow reaction mixture was diluted with (40 ml) petroleum ether (60–80 °C) and filtered to remove suspended impurities. The solvent was then removed by distillation under vacuum. The whole operation was repeated with (40 ml) petroleum ether (60–80 °C) and finally the petroleum ether solvent was distilled off. Phenyl isocyanodichloride (7 ml) in the form of pale yellow oil was collected (Found : N, 1.95. Requires : 8.04%).

Note

Synthesis of 2-phenylimino-3-aryl-4-S-benzyl-6-hepta-O-benzoyl-β-D-lactosylimino-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochlorides (3a-g) :

A solution of phenyl isocyanodichloride **2** (0.005 M in 15 ml CHCl₃) was added to a solution of 1-aryl-5-hepta-O-benzoyl-β-D-lactosyl-2-S-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**1a-g**) (0.005 M in 20 ml CHCl₃) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h. Afterwards the solvent was distilled off to obtain a sticky residue. This residue was triturated with petroleum ether (60–80 °C, 60 ml) to afford a pale yellow solid (**3a-g**). The products were crystallized with acetone-petroleum ether.

On extending the reaction of 1-aryl-5-hepta-O-benzoyl-β-D-lactosyl-2-S-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets with phenyl isocyanodichloride several 2-phenylimino-3-aryl-4-S-benzyl-6-hepta-O-benzoyl-β-D-lactosylimino-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochlorides have been isolated (Table 1). IR¹⁰, NMR¹¹ and Mass¹² spectra of the products were observed. Optical rotation¹³ of the products were also recorded.

3c : m.p. 132 °C; yield 89%; [α]_D²⁵ + 97° (c. 0.140 in CHCl₃); IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1729.2 (C=O), 1450.4 (C-N), 1268.3 (C-O), 854.4 (lactosyl C-H deformation), 707.1 (C-H aromatic); ¹H NMR (ppm) : δ 8.10–7.18 (49H, m, 7COC₆H₅, 2C₆H₅, C₆H₄), 5.74–3.90 (16H, m, lactosyl protons, S-CH₂), 2.26 (3H, s, -CH₃); Mass (*m/z*) : 1468 (M⁺), 1469 (M⁺+1), 1052 (HBL⁺), 579 (TBG⁺), 391 (TBG⁺-C₁₂H₁₂O₂), 335 (TBG-C₁₄H₁₂O₄), 105 (C₆H₅CO⁺) (Found : C, 68.55; H, 4.58; N, 3.78; S, 4.25. Calcd. for C₈₄H₆₈O₁₇N₄S₂: C, 68.66; H, 4.63; N, 3.81; S, 4.35%).

3f : m.p. 142–144 °C; yield 82%; [α]_D²⁵+94° (c. 0.140 in CHCl₃); IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1728.5 (C=O), 1451.2 (C-N), 1271 (C-O), 854.4 (lactosyl C-H deformation), 709.7 (C-H aromatic); ¹H NMR (ppm) : δ 8.05–7.28 (49H, m, 7COC₆H₅, 2C₆H₅, C₆H₄), 5.74–3.89 (16H, m, lactosyl protons, S-CH₂); Mass (*m/z*) : 1489 (M⁺), 1490 (M⁺+1), 1052 (HBL⁺), 579 (TBG⁺), 391 (TBG⁺-C₁₂H₁₂O₂), 335 (TBG-C₁₄H₁₂O₄), 105 (C₆H₅CO⁺)

Table 1. 2-Phenylimino-3-aryl-4-S-benzyl-6-hepta-O-benzoyl-β-D-lactosylimino-2,3-dihydro-1,3,5-thiadiazine hydrochlorides (**3a-g**) (Scheme 1)

Reactants : (I) 1-Aryl-5-hepta-O-benzoyl-β-D-lactosyl-2-S-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**1a-g**) (0.005 M, 6.7 g in 20 ml CHCl₃). (II) phenyl isocyanodichloride (**2**) (0.005 M in 15 ml CHCl₃)

Product	Melting point (°C)	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found (Requires)		[α] _D ²⁵ (c. CHCl ₃)
			S	N	
3a	118	85	3.83 (3.85)	4.31 (4.40)	+118° (c. 0.140)
3b	148	82	3.80 (3.81)	4.30 (4.35)	+129° (c. 0.140)
3c	132	89	3.78 (3.81)	4.25 (4.35)	+97° (c. 0.140)
3d	138	87	3.80 (3.81)	4.25 (4.35)	+138° (c. 0.140)
3e	140	90	3.73 (3.76)	4.25 (4.30)	+109° (c. 0.140)
3f	144	82	3.73 (3.76)	4.21 (4.30)	+94° (c. 0.140)
3g	148	89	3.78 (3.76)	4.21 (4.30)	+116° (c. 0.140)

C and H analysis were found satisfactory in all cases.

3a : m.p. 118 °C; yield 85%; [α]_D²⁵ + 118° (c. 0.140 in CHCl₃); IR (KBr) (cm⁻¹) : 1729 (C=O), 1451.2 (C-N), 1271 (C-O), 854.4 (lactosyl C-H deformation), 709.9 (C-H aromatic); ¹H NMR (ppm) : δ 8.15–7.18 (50H, m, 7COC₆H₅, 3C₆H₅), 5.74–3.79 (16H, m, lactosyl protons, S-CH₂); Mass (*m/z*) : 1454 (M⁺), 1455 (M⁺+1), 1052 (HBL⁺), 579 (TBG⁺), 391 (TBG⁺-C₁₂H₁₂O₂), 335 (TBG-C₁₄H₁₂O₄), 105 (C₆H₅CO⁺) (Found : C, 68.45; H, 4.50; N, 3.83; S, 4.31. Calcd. for C₈₃H₆₆O₁₇N₄S₂ : C, 68.50; H, 4.53; N, 3.85; S, 4.40%).

(Found : C, 66.89; H, 4.30; N, 3.73; S, 4.21. Calcd. for C₈₃H₆₅O₁₇N₄S₂Cl : C, 66.92; H, 4.36; N, 3.76; S, 4.30%).

Antimicrobial activities :

All the compounds have been screened for both antibacterial and antifungal activity using cup plate agar diffusion method by measuring the inhibition zone in mm. The compounds were taken at a concentration of 1 mg/ml using dimethyl sulphoxide as solvent. Amikacin (100 µg/ml) was used as a standard for antibacterial and antifun-

Table 2. Antimicrobial activities of compounds (3a-g)

Compd.	Antibacterial ^a			Antifungal ^b		
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. vulgaris</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>C. guilliermondii</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
3a	17	22	23	24	20	20
3b	23	19	18	23	23	23
3c	19	19	20	23	20	22
3d	15	19	17	19	20	22
3e	15	14	18	20	20	22
3f	15	22	23	16	22	22
3g	17	24	22	23	21	22
Amikacin	18	21	23	24	-	-
Fluconazole	-	-	-	-	24	25

^aIncluding the well diameter of 8 mm. ^bZone of inhibition in mm (15 or less) less resistance, (16-20 mm) moderate and (more than 20 mm) sensitive.

gal activity and fluconazole (100 µg/ml) as a standard for antifungal activity. The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Salmonella typhi* in nutrient agar medium and for antifungal activity against *Candida guilliermondii* and *Microsporum* in potato dextrose agar medium.

It has been observed that all of these compounds showed nearly the same activity as that of the standard fluconazole and amikacin (Table 2). Similarly it has also been observed that some of these compounds exhibited interesting microbial activities. 3a, 3b, 3c and 3g exhibited most significant activity against *Salmonella typhi* and *E. coli* while 3f inhibited *S. aureus* and *P. vulgaris*. All other compounds exhibited low to moderate activity.

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